

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: GAUTAM****FIRST NAME: BHARAT****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied USThe author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)

WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

When I came to know about Euclid University and the several Ph.D. programs available online, I was excited and did not take long to choose a program and make this decision to enroll. However, I had to request a delay for a few months to fix some processes.

For several years, I practiced informal writing at work, which was neither structured nor systematic. It was largely the practice of writing field reports, training proceedings, or meeting minutes. I am curious to learn from the respective academicians and looking forward to an active journey of learning.

The purpose of this response paper is to reflect on the course pack that provides light on academic writing, which was developed by Prof. Laurent Cleenerck and Dr Gulma, Kabiru. I am reflecting briefly on essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, rules of style, and US vs. UK English.

2) ESSAY WRITING

For a long period of time, I have been living with curiosity around writing in a way that becomes appealing and convincing to the general people so that people can be attentive and remain inspired in action. Academic writing is simply referred to as a process of ‘brainstorming the ideas’ as many as possible, ‘narrowing the focus’ as specific as possible to a particular theme, and ‘explain why one argument is more convincing than another and how they relate to the conclusion’ (EUCLID 2021, 9).

I find the structure useful (a) introducing the idea, (b) answering the key questions supported by facts, (c) summarizing the key points, and most importantly, taking time to read and think before writing, analyzing, and presenting the answers to the questions (EUCLID 2021, 7).

I used to write, and the next day, I used to hate my own writing. I have read the rule of thumb, and I concur with the instructions for writing short sentences, avoiding page-long paragraphs, and not repeating the same words (EUCLID 2021, 13).

These days, it is difficult to attract the attention of the people either by speaking or by delivering speeches. I also concur that academic writing is not the way to fill some space, and it is important to stay focused on the main argument and just get right to the point (EUCLID 2021, 13).

3) PUNCTUATION

I have gone through the punctuation, chapter two (2) of the course pack and I found various simple and useful tips that support and improve the writing. Actually, I immediately started applying at my work while writing memo, emails and feedbacks. Some instructions such as do and do not list to use apostrophe, brackets, bullet points, colon, semicolon, comma, dashes and hyphens. I was reading and using some of these without knowing the meaning. I was not aware and never separated the meaning some of these punctuations such as round brackets, square brackets, angle and curly brackets. Proper use of punctuations might help making the messages smooth however in academic writing it is recommended to use as little punctuation as necessary (EUCLID 2021, 16).

4) PLAGIARISM

I have read the chapter on plagiarism with deep interest. I thought it was difficult to balance knowing how much to reference, and I was not aware there was software available (as I have never used it) that indicates the level of plagiarism. The solution to managing plagiarism does not seem difficult. It is simply consistent to follow and give credit to the author when using any quote, paraphrase, statistics, or visuals (EUCLID 2021, 34).

I had the impression that by acknowledging the author, it would be fine to use the reference to support the argument, but I have felt that I need to be careful in my future project, as it should not be dominated by the references and I concur if I use too much, it does not look like my own research and I agree, only references guard against the plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34).

It is clear that plagiarism is a behavior that attracts disciplinary action immediately. This is not only about using academic content without acknowledgment but self-plagiarism also and reuses their own previously disseminated content without letting the readers know that material has appeared previously (Roig 2015, 16).

Reflecting on the chapter on plagiarism, I think attempting plagiarism is an insult to the reader and to the respective teacher.

5) **STYLE GUIDE**

Something that was a bit new for me was the ‘style guide,’ and I need to learn more about this. I have started learning deeply about the Chicago Rules as the style guide seems an essential guideline, and I am sure it will help me and ‘allow me to deliver my assignments in acceptable form’ (EUCLID 2021, 41).

6) **CONCLUSION**

The first session of my very first course was a very good orientation. As I come from a region where English is not an official language, I have realized well that I need to go through all the learning materials, references, and related video tutorials. I also need to fix the Zotero and Grammarly soon in my application so that I can apply these effectively. I am optimistic, and I am excited and willing to maximize this opportunity for learning. For several years, I practiced open-style writing, and I look forward to this opportunity for guided academic writing. I find the contents well designed, processes are well navigated, and the learning platform is very much learning-centered and navigated to the needs of students.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

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Miguel Roig. 2015. *A Guide to Ethical Writing*. Second Revision.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.